

INTERACTION OF HYDROXYACETOPHENONES AND THEIR DERIVATIVES
AND THIONYL CHLORIDE IN PRESENCE OF FINELY DIVIDED COPPER.
PART VII. PRÉPARATION OF 3:3'-DIACETYL- AND 3:3'-DIPROPIONYL-
4:4'-DIHYDROXY-5:5'-DIMETHYLDIPHENYL SULPHIDES
AND THEIR DERIVATIVES

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Preparation of 3:3'-diacetyl- and 3:3'-dipropionyl-4:4'-dihydroxy-5:5'-dimethyldiphenyl sulphides is described. Their diacetoxy derivatives and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones as well as nitration products are also described.

Present work is the extension of the work of Jadhav and Merchant (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1951, 19, Part V, 41) and has been carried out with a view to studying the effect of the introduction of Me group in the nucleus of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone towards the reaction of thionyl chloride in presence of finely divided copper, as well as the effect of lengthening the chain attached to the ketonic group in that reaction. Introduction of Me group had practically no effect on the reactivity of the ketone, as the sulphide (I) was formed only when the reactants were allowed to react directly at a low temperature, similar to the case of simple *o*-hydroxyacetophenone.

Lengthening of the chain of the ketone deactivated the molecule further, as the reaction mixture required heating to complete the reaction.

Pure sulphides could be obtained with difficulty in both the cases, as described in the Experimental.

The same sulphide (I) was also obtained by the action of sulphur monochloride and sulphur dichloride on 2-hydroxy-3-methylacetophenone, and the sulphide (II) was prepared by the action of sulphur dichloride on 2-hydroxy-3-propioiphenone in presence of copper.

The presence of -OH and -CO groups in the sulphides was proved by preparing their acetoxy and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivatives.

The position of sulphur linking was located by nitrating the sulphides in presence of sulphuric acid, when both the sulphides furnished the same 2-methyl-4:6-dinitrophenol (3:5-dinitro-*o*-cresol, Me=1). This showed that one nitro group came in place of the ketonic group and the other in place of the sulphur atom which had linked the nuclei. As the ketonic group is in the position-6 (-OH=1), sulphur linking must be in the position-4, which is *para* to -OH group and *meta* to -CO group.

The replacement of the ketonic group by the nitro group must have taken place by its first being oxidised to -COOH and then this -COOH group was replaced by the nitro group, as such replacement of the COOH group by NO₂ group had already been reported by Hirve, Jadhav and Chakradeo (*ibid.*, 1934, 11, 554), who obtained 2-methyl-4:5:6-trinitrophenol from 3:3'-dicarboxy-4:4'-dihydroxy-5:5'-dimethyldiphenyl sulphide.

The mechanism of the reaction may be explained in the same way as has been done by Hirve *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 101).

EXPERIMENTAL

3:3'-Diacetyl-4:4'-dihydroxy-5:5'-dimethyldiphenyl Sulphide (I).—Thionyl chloride (5 c.c.) was added to 2-hydroxy-3-methylacetophenone (3-acetyl-*o*-cresol, Me = 1) (3 c.c.) and copper powder (2 g.) was gradually added to it (over a period of 2 hours). The reaction was allowed to proceed overnight at room temperature, the mixture having been protected from moisture. It was then first washed with dry ether and then extracted with boiling benzene. On removal of the benzene a yellowish white paste remained, which solidified on treatment with acetone. It was finally crystallised from chloroform. It sintered at 155° and completely liquefied at 240-41°, yield 0.8 g. (Found: C, 65.5; H, 5.5; S, 0.5. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4S$ requires C, 65.5; H, 5.4; S, 9.7 per cent).

The same sulphide was obtained from the ketone (3 c.c.) and sulphur dichloride (3 c.c.) by interacting them on a boiling water-bath for 3 hours and then leaving the reaction mixture overnight at room temperature, and also by the interaction of the ketone (3 c.c.) and sulphur monochloride and leaving them overnight at room temperature.

3:3'-Diacetyl-4:4'-diacetoxy-5:5'-dimethyldiphenyl sulphide was prepared by interacting the sulphide (I) and acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 105-106°. (Found: S, 7.8. $C_{22}H_{22}O_6S$ requires S, 7.7 per cent).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* of the above diphenyl sulphide (I) was crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 187°. (Found: S, 4.8. $C_{20}H_{16}O_{10}N_2S$ requires S, 4.6 per cent).

*2-Methyl-4:6-dinitrophenol (3:5-Dinitro-*o*-cresol).*—The sulphide (I) (1 g.) was suspended in H_2SO_4 (20 c.c.) and HNO_3 (conc., 15 c.c.) was added to it when a clear yellowish solution was obtained. It was left overnight at room temperature and then diluted and extracted with ether. The solid obtained after removal of the ether was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 86-87°. (Found: N, 13.9. Calc. for $C_7H_6O_6N_2$: N, 14.1 per cent). Rapp (*Annalen*, 1884, **224**, 175) reports m.p. 85-88°. No lowering in melting point was observed when mixed with a genuine specimen.

The same dinitro-*o*-cresol was obtained when the sulphide (II) was treated with nitric acid in presence of sulphuric acid.

3:3'-Dipropionyl-4:4'-dihydroxy-5:5'-dimethyldiphenyl Sulphide (II).—Copper powder (2 g.) was gradually added to the mixture of 2-hydroxy-3-methylpropionophenone (3 c.c.) and thionyl chloride (5 c.c.). Half an hour after the addition of copper was over the mixture was refluxed on a boiling water-bath for 3 hours. When cold, the mixture was extracted with chloroform. The red paste obtained after removal of the solvent was repeatedly washed with petroleum ether and then subjected to the action of steam for ½ hour. When cooled, a red solid separated. It was finally crystallised from benzene, m.p. 98°. (Found: C, 67.1; H, 6.2; S, 9.1. $C_{20}H_{16}O_4S$ requires C, 67.0; H, 6.1; S, 8.9 per cent).

It is very soluble in acetone, chloroform, carbon disulphide, sparingly so in benzene, very sparingly in ether, acetic acid, and insoluble in alcohol and petroleum ether.

The same sulphide was obtained by allowing the ketone (3 c.c.), sulphur dichloride (2 c.c.) and copper powder (1 g.) to react overnight at room temperature.

3:3'-Dipropionyl-4:4'-diacetoxy-5:5'-dimethyldiphenyl sulphide was prepared by the action of acetic anhydride on the sulphide (II) in presence of pyridine. It crystallised from benzene, m.p. 75-76°. (Found : S, 7.0. $C_{24}H_{28}O_8S$ requires S, 7.2 per cent).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of the above diphenyl sulphide (II) was crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 86-87°. (Found : S, 4.6. $C_{22}H_{20}O_{10}N_2S$ requires S, 4.5 per cent).

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